

Physico-Mechanical Properties of Hybrid Wood Plastic Composite

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Abstract

The work studied the physico-mechanical properties of hybrid composite sheets made from chemically modified mango seed (*Magnifera indica*) shell and Balanite desert date (*Balanite aegyptiaca*) shell as reinforcements in high density polyethylene (HDPE) as matrix. The particle size was 150 μm (15 μm). The sheets were molded using a Saumya compression molding machine in Mango/Balanite fibre ratio of 100/0; 70/30; 50/50; 30/70 and 0/100 after milling on a Saumya two roll mill machine. The mechanical, hardness and swelling behaviour properties of the sheets were then evaluated. The tests revealed that the sample with 50/50 fibre loading has the highest young modulus and tensile strength at 1770.83 N/mm^2 and 12.50 N/mm^2 respectively while the sample with fibre ratio 30/70 comes closest to it at 956.25 N/mm^2 for young modulus and 9.21 N/mm^2 for tensile strength. The hardness test revealed that the sample with 30/70 fibre loading has the highest value at 71 shore D which was also closely followed by the sample at 50/50 fibre loading at 60.8 shore D. Sample with the fibre ratio of 30/70 also shows highest elongation and swelling.

Keywords: *Balanite aegyptiaca*, Hybrid, *Magnifera indica*, Wood Polymer Composite

1.0 Introduction

Fibre reinforced composite materials constitute an important class of engineering materials. These materials offer outstanding mechanical properties, unique flexibility in design capabilities and ease of fabrication. The potential of plant fibre as reinforcement in composite materials have been well recognized since about 3,000 years ago, when the Egyptians used straw reinforced clay to build walls [1,2,3,4]. Polymer composites based on natural fibres are currently attracting great interest as alternative materials to synthetic fibre reinforced plastics in several applications, mostly automotive, building and packaging products [5]. In any case, the development of hybrid composites using natural fibres becomes an attractive research area and a possible substitute for synthetic fibre composites due to the non-recyclability, high density and health hazards as well as environmental pollution associated with composites reinforced with synthetic fibres such as glass, carbon and aramid fibres [5]. A major challenge of using synthetic fibre reinforced materials is how to conveniently and safely

dispose of them once they have come to the end of their useful life span [6]. As a result, there has been growing interest in the use of natural cellulosic fibres as reinforcement for polymeric matrix [7]. Several natural fibres such as sisal [8]; jute [9]; flax [10]; bamboo [11]; kenaf [12]; bagasse [13], fibres have been studied as a reinforcement and filler in polymer composites. This work incorporates *Balanite aegyptiaca* and *Magnifera indica*.

Balanite aegyptiaca is a member of the Zygophyllaceae family. It is commonly known as Desert date. It is a multi-branched, spiny shrub or tree that grows up to 10 m tall. The tree trunk is short and often branches near the base. It has a dark brown to grey bark and is deeply fissured [14].

The pulp is edible and has a bitter-sweet taste. The seed or kernel ranges from light to dark brown in colour. It is fibrous and extremely hard with a cracking pressure of $10.4 \times 10^5 \text{ N/m}^2$ as reported by Mohammed [15].

Mango (*Mangifera indica*) is a perennial crop of the family Anacardiaceae. It is grown practically all over tropical and sub-tropical regions of the world. The fruits are oval or kidney shaped with smooth, leathery skin and the colour ranges from light or dark green to clear yellow when ripe. The pulp of the fruit is consumed fresh as a dessert or processed in to juices, jams and other products [16]. Mango seed is a single flat oblong seed that can be fibrous or hairy on the surface, depending on the cultivar. Mango seed consists of a tenacious coat enclosing the kernel. Kordylas [17] has however, reported that the seeds have been used in compounding animal feed. The seed content of different varieties of mangoes ranges from 9% to 23% of the fruit weight [18] and the kernel content of the seed ranges from 45.7% to 72.8% [19].

High Density Polyethylene (HDPE) a thermoplastic, is selected as the matrix material for this study, and this is in agreement with the general trend for industrially fabricated plant fibre composites where thermoplastics are increasingly being used in preference to thermosetting polymers [2, 3].

2.0 Materials and Methods

The materials and methods adopted are presented as follows:

2.1 Materials

The materials used were mango seed shell (*Mangifera indica*), which was gotten from Alaba suru (a mango market in Lagos main land) and balanite nut shell (*Balanite aegyptiaca*), which was gotten from Yola in Adamawa State. High density polyethylene (HDPE) was got from a plastic production company (Poly product, Oshodi, Lagos). Other materials were Standard BSS 100 sieve, Sodium hydroxide (NaOH) (Analar grade), Kerosene standard commercial grade, distilled water (H₂O) and Petroleum spirit (Analar grade), and Xylene (Analar grade). The equipment used included Hydraulic Compression Molding Machine (Saumya technocrats Hycon-20T). Two roll mill (Saumya technocrates DTRM-150). Universal Testing Machine Saumya technocrats VTM-122. Durometer OS2H. Others were scissors, gloves and weighing balance-BOMANN-614151 and British Standard Test Sieve manufactured by Wykeham Farrance Slough, England.

2.2 Alkali treatment of the fibres

The fibres were pulverized and thereafter immersed in NaOH solution with a concentration of 20% for 24 hours at room temperature (to remove natural impurities such as lignin, waxes etc). After treatment, the fibres were washed with 2% acetic acid (to remove residual NaOH) and again washed with distilled water then finally air dried for 48 hours.

2.3 Milling

The matrix (HDPE) was milled using the two roll mill at 105 °C. The rolls rotate at different speed to create a shearing action to the trough formed between them. The fibre mixture was then added in predetermined formulations for at least 5 minutes. The milling continued till a homogeneous composite was obtained. The composite was then allowed to cool. A compression molding hydraulic machine was used to mould the material at 130 °C and cured for 3 minutes. Five different samples were gotten according to Table 1. Fibre reinforced composite materials constitute an important class of engineering materials. These materials offer outstanding mechanical properties, unique flexibility in design capabilities and ease of fabrication. The potential of plant fibre as reinforcement in composite materials have been well recognized since about 3,000 years ago, when the Egyptians used straw reinforced clay to build walls [1,2,3,4]. Polymer composites based on natural fibres are currently attracting great interest as alternative materials to synthetic fibre reinforced plastics in several applications, mostly automotive, building and packaging products [5]. In any case, the development of hybrid composites using natural fibres becomes an attractive research area and a possible substitute for synthetic fibre composites due to the non-recyclability, high density and health hazards as well as environmental pollution associated with composites reinforced with synthetic fibres such as glass, carbon and aramid fibres [5]. A major challenge of using synthetic fibre reinforced materials is how to conveniently and safely dispose of them once they have come to the end of their useful life span [6]. As a result, there has been growing interest in the use of natural cellulosic fibres as reinforcement for polymeric matrix [7]. Several natural fibres such as sisal [8]; jute [9]; flax [10]; bamboo [11]; kenaf [12]; bagasse [13], fibres have been studied as a reinforcement and filler in polymer composites.

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Table 1: Sample of HDPE and filler ratio.

SAMPLE	HDPE (g)	Filler (g)		Filler Ratio (%)	
		BALANITE	MANGO	BALANITE	MANGO
A	50	50	0	100	0
B	50	35	15	70	30
C	50	25	25	50	50
D	50	15	35	30	70
E	50	0	50	0	100

Table 2: Data Analysis Table.

SAMPLE	Hardness (Shore D)	Elongation @ break (mm)	Tensile Strength (N/mm ²)	Young Modulus (N/mm ²) x 10 ²
A	47.60	4.30	1.13	1.02
B	53.30	3.23	6.80	7.86
C	60.80	3.00	12.50	17.71
D	71.00	5.33	9.21	9.56
E	51.90	1.60	1.38	5.31

2.4 Characterization of Composite Materials

The composite materials were characterized as follows:

2.4.1 Water Absorption Determination

These tests were carried out using ASTM D 570 standard. Specimens of 40 mm x 40 mm were cut out of the main composites sheet and immersed in distilled water for 24 hours at room temperature. The ratio of increase in mass of the specimen to the initial mass is given as the percentage moisture absorption. Mathematically, water absorption (W_A) was calculated using equation (1).

$$W_A = \frac{W_w - W_d}{W_d} \times 100 \% \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

$$W_d$$

Where, W_w = Wet Weight and W_d = Dry Weight

2.4.2 Swelling Behaviour Determination

Specimens of 40 x 40 mm were cut out of each main composites sheet, weighed dried (W_i), immersed in 200 ml volume of kerosene, petroleum, xylene and toluene solvent (five (5) each) at room temperature for 24 hours respectively. Thereafter, the specimens were filtered and excess solvent was patted dry with lint free cloth then the final weight (W_f) was noted. The percent swelling was calculated using equation (2).

$$P_s = \frac{W_f - W_i}{W_i} \times 100 \% \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

$$W_i$$

2.4.3 Hardness Determination

Hardness measurement was done using a Leitz Hardness (OS-2H) tester. This tester had a diamond indenter, in form of a right pyramid with a square base. At an angle of 136° between opposite faces, it was used to hold the material

under a load of 3 N in accordance with ASTM E384.

2.4.4 Strength Determination

The tensile properties of the specimens were determined using dumb bell shaped samples. The gauge length between the jaws at the start of each test was adjusted to 40 mm and the measurements carried out at a crosshead speed of 5 mm/min according to ASTM D638-99 (ISO-527-99). The stress-strain curves were then plotted and the ultimate tensile strength, Young's modulus and % elongation at break were determined for respective composite sample.

3.0 Results and Discussion

The Results and Discussion were presented as follows:

3.1. Water Absorption Determination

Fig 1. Water Absorption of Mango/Balanite fibre at different filler loadings ratio.

From Fig. 1, The Mango/Balanite fibre of ratio 1:1 (50/50) had a water absorption value of 5.6% which is considerably low when compared to other samples. This is corroborated by an earlier report on Luffa and Balanite hybrid composite by Ichetaonye and Akindiya [20]. This is due to low porosity and better interfacial relationship within the fibres and matrix. The general trend is that as the Balanite fibre increases in fibre loading ratio, the percentage swelling also increases though in no particular order. This suggests that Balanite fibre have slightly more affinity for moisture when compared to Mango fibres. De [21] reported similar trend for short fibres loadings.

3.2. Swelling Behaviour Determination

Fig. 2 shows the swelling behaviour of the samples in selected solvents. Clearly, all the samples show very high swelling in toluene except for sample with filler ratio 70/30 (Mango/Balanite fibres) which showed high swelling in petrol. Furthermore, all the samples showed the least swelling in kerosene of all the solvents. This is due to reduced macro – cracks, better fill – up of gaps between the fibres and matrix. Ichetaonye and Akindiya [20,22] had reported similar trend.

Fig. 2: Swelling Behaviour of Mango/Balanite fibre at different filler loadings ratio in selected solvent.

3.3. Hardness Determination

Fig. 3 revealed that there was a gradual increase in hardness for all reinforced composites material as the Balanite loading increases in the filler loading ratio. The maximum hardness value of 71 shore D was exhibited by 30/70 filler loading ratio was due to the better solid state fusion between the fibres and matrix, also, the breaking down of -OH group in cellulose and lignin as well as the higher reduction of internal pores particularly accounts for the moderately high hardness values in the composites. Composite samples with no Balanite and Mango fibre showed the least hardness values. This suggests that both fibre have contributed synergistically to the hardness of the composites. In a report on mechanical properties of hybrid wood/clay polymer composites, Alebiosu [23] asserts that improved interfacial interactions contributes to the overall mechanical performance of fibre reinforced composites.

Fig. 3: Hardness of Mango/Balanite fibre at different filler loadings ratio.

As seen in Fig 4, the composite sample with 30/70 (Mango/Balanite fibres) filler loading has the highest elongation at break value of 5.33 mm while the least was the 0/100 sample at 1.60 mm. This shows that the sample with fibre loading 30/70 has the highest (elasticity) resistance to fracture when compared to other samples. This is because the fibre composition at 30/70 tends to properly distribute the load across the composite material due to good interfacial interaction and as a result, it could bear load further longer when compared to other fibre loading ratios. A similar trend was also supported by Kahlil [24].

Fig 4: Elongation at break for Mango/Balanite fibre at different filler loadings ratio.

Fig 5 below is the graph of young modulus of the composites at different fibre loadings. Fibre loading at 50/50 (Mango/Balanite fibres) shows the highest young modulus and it is closely followed by composite with fibre loading of 30/70 (Mango/Balanite fibres). Generally, Young modulus of fibres improves with alkali treatment. This was also corroborated by Oladele [25]. Sample with fibre loading of 50/50 (Mango/Balanite fibres) has equal ratio of both fibres which indicates the minimum of both fibres

that imparted the Young's modulus of the composite and it is also indicative of good interfacial bond. Karnana [26] and Oladele [27] reported a similar trend.

Fig 5: Young Modulus for Mango/Balanite fibre at different filler loadings ratio.

Fig 6: Tensile Strength for Mango/Balanite fibre at different filler loadings ratio

The tensile strength is as shown in fig 6 above. Composite at fibre loading of 50/50 (Mango/Balanite fibres) showed the highest tensile strength. This is indicative of improved adhesive characteristic which doesn't allow fibre pull out. This might not be unconnected with the alkali treatment which removed non adhering constituents of the fibre [22]. Hence, at this fibre loading, there is good cohesiveness between fibre and matrix. Oladele [27] and Joseph [28] also opined that tensile properties of fibres significantly improves with chemical treatment.

Fig.7: Plot of Hardness and Elongation.

Figure 7 shows the plot of hardness and elongation at break. Clearly, as the mango filler ratio increases, from sample A to E, the hardness also increases though the *Balanite* filler ratio decreases. Hence, hardness and elongation at break shows a linear relationship with the mango filler while it has an inverse relationship with *Balanite* filler. Both hardness and elongation have peak values at sample D (30% *Balanite*/70% Mango) and a sharp decrease at sample E. Hence, sample D is the optimum ratio of the fillers [23].

Fig.8: Plot of Tensile strength and Young Modulus

As seen in fig. 8, tensile strength increases as Young modulus increases. This trend however peaked at the 50/50% filler ratio at sample C. This trend is attributable to increase in the longer mango fibre filler reinforcement [23]. Beyond the

50/50 filler ratio, any further increase in mango filler showed a decrease in tensile strength and Young modulus. Hence mango fibre shows better reinforcing properties than *Balanite* though at higher loading, it increases ductility of the material.

4.0 Conclusion

The Physico-mechanical properties of modified Mango/*Balanite aegyptiaca* HDPE hybrid composites were investigated and on the basis of experimental evidences shown in the various Figures, it can be concluded that 50/50 % composites showed superior values with best improved mechanical properties followed by 30/70 % composites. Samples with fibre loading 0/100, 100/0 exhibits the least properties values especially for hardness, tensile strength, and Young modulus. This is one of the few attempts to produce high performance composites using materials predominantly found in nature.

5.0 Recommendation

Based on this study, it is recommended that further work be done on surface modification and degree of crystallization of chemically modified fibre reinforced composite.

6.0 Acknowledgements

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7.0 Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

8.0 Reference

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